
A NEW PROOF OF CONTINUOUS WELCH BOUNDS

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Abstract: We give a new proof of continuous Welch bounds obtained by M. Krishna [*arXiv:2109.09296*]. Our proof is motivated from the proof of Welch [*IEEE Transactions on Information Theory, 1974*].

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1. A NEW PROOF OF CONTINUOUS WELCH BOUNDS

In [1], following continuous version of Welch bounds are proved using (continuous) frames/spectral theory.

Theorem 1.1. [1] *Let (Ω, μ) be a measure space and $\{\tau_\alpha\}_{\alpha \in \Omega}$ be a normalized continuous Bessel family for a d -dimensional Hilbert space \mathcal{H} . If the diagonal $\Delta := \{(\alpha, \alpha) : \alpha \in \Omega\}$ is measurable in the measure space $\Omega \times \Omega$, then*

$$(1) \quad \int_{\Omega \times \Omega} |\langle \tau_\alpha, \tau_\beta \rangle|^{2m} d(\mu \times \mu)(\alpha, \beta) = \int_{\Omega} \int_{\Omega} |\langle \tau_\alpha, \tau_\beta \rangle|^{2m} d\mu(\alpha) d\mu(\beta) \geq \frac{\mu(\Omega)^2}{\binom{d+m-1}{m}}, \quad \forall m \in \mathbb{N}.$$

*Equality holds in Inequality (1) if and only if $\{\tau_\alpha\}_{\alpha \in \Omega}$ is a tight continuous frame. Further, we have the **higher order continuous Welch bounds***

$$(2) \quad \sup_{\alpha, \beta \in \Omega, \alpha \neq \beta} |\langle \tau_\alpha, \tau_\beta \rangle|^{2m} \geq \frac{1}{(\mu \times \mu)((\Omega \times \Omega) \setminus \Delta)} \left[\frac{\mu(\Omega)^2}{\binom{d+m-1}{m}} - (\mu \times \mu)(\Delta) \right], \quad \forall m \in \mathbb{N}.$$

*In particular, we have the **first order continuous Welch bound***

$$\sup_{\alpha, \beta \in \Omega, \alpha \neq \beta} |\langle \tau_\alpha, \tau_\beta \rangle|^2 \geq \frac{1}{(\mu \times \mu)((\Omega \times \Omega) \setminus \Delta)} \left[\frac{\mu(\Omega)^2}{d} - (\mu \times \mu)(\Delta) \right].$$

Proof. We give a new proof. Due to unitary equivalence of any two same dimensional Hilbert spaces, it suffices to prove the theorem for the standard d -dimensional Hilbert space \mathbb{C}^d . Our proof is motivated from the proof of Welch [2]. Let $\tau_\alpha := (a_1^{(\alpha)}, a_2^{(\alpha)}, \dots, a_d^{(\alpha)})$ for all $\alpha \in \Omega$. Define

$$B_m := \int_{\Omega \times \Omega} |\langle \tau_\alpha, \tau_\beta \rangle|^{2m} d(\mu \times \mu)(\alpha, \beta) = \int_{\Omega} \int_{\Omega} |\langle \tau_\alpha, \tau_\beta \rangle|^{2m} d\mu(\alpha) d\mu(\beta).$$

Then

$$\begin{aligned} B_m &= \int_{\Delta} |\langle \tau_\alpha, \tau_\beta \rangle|^{2m} d(\mu \times \mu)(\alpha, \beta) + \int_{(\Omega \times \Omega) \setminus \Delta} |\langle \tau_\alpha, \tau_\beta \rangle|^{2m} d(\mu \times \mu)(\alpha, \beta) \\ &= (\mu \times \mu)(\Delta) + \int_{(\Omega \times \Omega) \setminus \Delta} |\langle \tau_\alpha, \tau_\beta \rangle|^{2m} d(\mu \times \mu)(\alpha, \beta) \\ &\leq (\mu \times \mu)(\Delta) + \sup_{\alpha, \beta \in \Omega, \alpha \neq \beta} |\langle \tau_\alpha, \tau_\beta \rangle|^{2m} (\mu \times \mu)((\Omega \times \Omega) \setminus \Delta). \end{aligned}$$

On the other hand, using the definition of standard inner product in \mathbb{C}^d and Cauchy-Schwarz inequality,

$$\begin{aligned}
B_m &= \int_{\Omega} \int_{\Omega} \left| \sum_{r=1}^d a_r^{(\alpha)} \overline{a_r^{(\beta)}} \right|^{2m} d\mu(\alpha) d\mu(\beta) \\
&= \int_{\Omega} \int_{\Omega} \sum_{u_1 \dots u_m=1, v_1 \dots v_m=1}^d \prod_{p=1}^m a_{u_p}^{(\alpha)} \overline{a_{v_p}^{(\alpha)}} a_{u_p}^{(\beta)} \overline{a_{v_p}^{(\beta)}} d\mu(\alpha) d\mu(\beta) \\
&= \sum_{x_1 \dots x_d, y_1 \dots y_d, \sum_{r=1}^d x_r = \sum_{s=1}^d y_s = m} \binom{m}{x_1, \dots, x_d} \binom{m}{y_1, \dots, y_d} \left| \int_{\Omega} \prod_{r=1}^d \left(a_r^{(\alpha)} \right)^{x_r} \overline{\left(a_r^{(\alpha)} \right)^{y_r}} d\mu(\alpha) \right|^2 \\
&\geq \sum_{x_1 \dots x_d, \sum_{r=1}^d x_r = m} \binom{m}{x_1, \dots, x_d}^2 \left| \int_{\Omega} \prod_{r=1}^d |a_r^{(\alpha)}|^{2x_r} d\mu(\alpha) \right|^2 \\
&\geq \frac{1}{\left\| \sum_{x_1 \dots x_d, \sum_{r=1}^d x_r = m} \right\|} \left| \sum_{x_1 \dots x_d, \sum_{r=1}^d x_r = m} \binom{m}{x_1, \dots, x_d} \int_{\Omega} \prod_{r=1}^d |a_r^{(\alpha)}|^{2x_r} d\mu(\alpha) \right|^2 \\
&= \frac{1}{\binom{d+m-1}{m}} \left| \sum_{x_1 \dots x_d, \sum_{r=1}^d x_r = m} \binom{m}{x_1, \dots, x_d} \int_{\Omega} \prod_{r=1}^d |a_r^{(\alpha)}|^{2x_r} d\mu(\alpha) \right|^2 \\
&= \frac{1}{\binom{d+m-1}{m}} \left| \int_{\Omega} \sum_{x_1 \dots x_d, \sum_{r=1}^d x_r = m} \binom{m}{x_1, \dots, x_d} \prod_{r=1}^d |a_r^{(\alpha)}|^{2x_r} d\mu(\alpha) \right|^2 \\
&= \frac{1}{\binom{d+m-1}{m}} \left| \int_{\Omega} \left(\sum_{p=1}^d a_p^{(\alpha)} \overline{a_p^{(\alpha)}} \right)^m d\mu(\alpha) \right|^2 \\
&= \frac{1}{\binom{d+m-1}{m}} \left| \int_{\Omega} (1)^m d\mu(\alpha) \right|^2 = \frac{\mu(\Omega)^2}{\binom{d+m-1}{m}}.
\end{aligned}$$

Hence

$$\begin{aligned}
(\mu \times \mu)(\Delta) + \sup_{\alpha, \beta \in \Omega, \alpha \neq \beta} |\langle \tau_{\alpha}, \tau_{\beta} \rangle|^{2m} (\mu \times \mu)((\Omega \times \Omega) \setminus \Delta) &\geq \int_{\Omega \times \Omega} |\langle \tau_{\alpha}, \tau_{\beta} \rangle|^{2m} d(\mu \times \mu)(\alpha, \beta) \\
&\geq \frac{\mu(\Omega)^2}{\binom{d+m-1}{m}}.
\end{aligned}$$

□

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